

Sampling in Shenzhen Bay: Biodiversity and environment

Diarmuid Chu

BASIS Bilingual Shenzhen

Ifini.heven333@163.com

Abstract

Shenzhen Bay was originally mud flat, but the coastline of nowadays days' Shenzhen Bay was artificial. In this summer, a sampling was done for studying the biodiversity of Shenzhen Bay. The sampling started in Shenzhen Bay at 5 P.M. which was the time that intertidal zone started to exist. The intertidal zone of Shenzhen was mostly composed of mud flats. Only the part beside the beach was filled with rocks. This feature is due to land reclamation, so that the original habitats of marine organisms were destroyed. The components of Shenzhen Bay's bio-community were mostly crabs, mudskipper, sea snail and oyster. After collecting those organisms, they were stored in a plastic box. For oyster, the shell was broken and the soft body was put into the centrifugal tube. By doing PCR, the biodiversity of this bay can be discovered.

1. Introduction

The target of this sampling is to observe the ecological environment of Shenzhen Bay. After sampling, the low biodiversity of Shenzhen Bay had been observed. This phenomenon is probably due to human activity. In 40 years before, Shenzhen Bay had experienced a reclamation. There were totally 1793.43 ha reclaimed during the reclamation [1]. The reclamation caused many negative effect, including damaging organisms' habitat, burying a lot of benthos and bringing pollution. Organism like fish, tidal crabs and polychaetes already lose a lot of habitats. SWIMS, a well-protected area in Hong Kong, on the other hand, has an abundant biomass [2]. This study is to reveal the low biodiversity of Shenzhen Bay and try to explain the reason behind it.

2. Methods

2.1. Sampling preparation

The intertidal marine organisms were collected at Shenzhen Bay (22.518612, 113.964459). After sampling, the organisms were putted in a plastic box filled with sea water. And the samples were taking back to lab and store one

night, during which aeration was provided to make sure that the organisms had sufficient oxygen. Samples and lysis solution were moved into the 2 mL centrifuge tube. Then, the samples were put into magnetic stirring pot in 50°C water bath for 2 hours.

After 2 hours, the centrifuge tubes with lysis solution-sample mixture were put in the centrifuge of 12000 g for 3 minutes. Then, 500 μ L supernatant was retrieved and 700 μ L Binding Buffer and 300 μ L anhydrous ethanol were added. The mixture was transferred into a spin column after it was inverted and mixed well. Afterward, the spin column was put in the centrifuge for 1 minute in 10000 g. When the centrifugal process was completed, the waste liquid was poured away and the PW (Wash) Buffer was added into the mixture. The mixture experienced same centrifugal process as above. Then, the Wash Buffer was added into the mixture and it was placed in the centrifuge in 10000 g for 1 minute. This process was repeated again.

The spin column experienced centrifugation for 1 minute of 10000 g and the spin column was transferred into a new 2 mL centrifuge tube. The 50 μ L distilled water was added into the spin column and it required the same centrifugal process as above. Finally, the purification of DNA was completed. The concentration of DNA was measured by Nanodrop.

2.2. Gel electrophoresis and PCR

The mitochondrial gene fragment encoding cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) was amplified by PCR. The PCR reaction mixture which contain 10 μ L Phanta Max Master Mix (P525-AA) from Vazyme, 2 μ L of primer mixture of LCO1490 (5' GGTCACAAATCATAAA-GATATTGG 3') and HCO2198 (5' TAAACTTCAGGGT-GACCAAAAATCA 3') and 500 ng of the extracted DNA template 's solution (volume of DNA template adjusted according to its concentration)

Received: 30 December 2023 Accepted: 05 February 2024

Published: 25 March 2024

Citation: Chu, D. (2024). Biodiversity and environment. The Young Scientist, 3(1), 29-32.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10935362>

Figure 1. A picture showing the changing of Shenzhen's coast line. The area inside the black line is Shenzhen Bay. Red star refers to sampling point. From Wang jianfang [1]

was added up to 20 μL by ddH₂O. PCR cycle were 4 min at 94 °C, 30 cycles of 30 s at 94 °C, 30 s at 45 °C, 30 s at 72 °C, and 7 min at 72 °C.

The 0.25g of agarose from Blowest Agarose and 25 mL distilled water were mixed. The mixture was microwave heated for 2 minutes in 80 °C. Then, the heated mixture was pour into the mold to make the agarose gel. When the gel was completed, the marker was loaded onto the leftmost gel's bottom. Afterward, the DNA mixture was added. These two liquids should be 1 μL . Gel electrophoresis started after the electric wires were connected. This process lasted for 20 minutes.

After receiving the DNA sequence code, the code was entered in BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search tool) to search the suitable species.

3. Results

From the Shenzhen Bay intertidal zone, 5 specimens of gastropod sea snail and 17 specimens of crustaceans had been collected, including 11 crab specimen, four gammarid amphipod specimen, one shrimp specimen, and one cirripede barnacle specimen (See Figure 1 and 2). In addition, one specimen of fish (mudskipper), one specimen of polychaeta and one specimen of flatworm were also collected. Those crab and gastropod were collected under the stone where the sun couldn't arrive. The gammarid, polychaeta,

shrimp and mudskipper were also collected under the stone, but they were in the mud which had some moisture. The barnacle was sampled at the surface of the stone. The most abundance organism was crab and it dominate 39% organisms of this site. There were 7 samples (SB-1, SB-9, SB-17, SB-18, SB-21, SB-26, SB-27) that were succeed identified. They covered from family Neritidae, Nereididae, Grapsidae, Varunidae. SB-1 and SB-9 were belonged to Neritidae which are gastropod. SB-21 and SB-26 were belonged to Nereididae which are polychaetae. The Grapsidae covered SB-17 and SB-18 who are crustaceans. SB-27 is only one who belong to Varunidae and it is also crustaceans. However, within this those 7 samples, there only 2 samples were correctly identified which are SB-1, SB-17 and SB-26. The graph at below is a table for the samples.

4. Discussion

There were totally five different type of marine organism that had been collected. Shenzhen Bay's biodiversity was relatively low comparing to Hong Kong's SWIMS (Swire Institute of Marine Science). This difference is due to the reclamation to Shenzhen Bay [1]. Now, the coast line of Shenzhen Bay are mostly artificial. Therefore, the ecological environment was highly damaged. Many marine organism lose their place for reproduction and their habitats were destroyed during the reclamation. Unlike Shenzhen Bay,

Figure 2. Collection of Shenzhen Bay’s sampling. (A-E) Sea snail. SB-1, SB-2, SB-3, SB-5, SB-25. (F-M) Crab. SB-4, SB-6, SB-11, SB-15 19, SB-22 24. (N-O) Gammarid. SB-12 14, SB-27. (P) Mudskipper. SB-10. (Q) Flatworm. SB-20. (R) Polychaete. SB-21. (S) Barnacle. SB-BAR.

Figure 3. A contrast of Shenzhen Bay’s sampling.

SWIMS had at least 34 different marine organisms [2], but Shenzhen Bay only had 6 different marine organisms. According to Changbai Mountain Aquatic Animal Atlas, gammarid should be living in sandy bottom layer [3]. This Shenzhen Bay’s intertidal zone was fitting this situation. Plus, gammarids are scavenger which means that they can eat everything, including rotten leaves, dead organism and other organism’s egg. Therefore, gammarid can live in Shenzhen Bay’s harsh environment. In Shenzhen Bay, many crabs (Grapsidae) were founded under rocks. There

are two reasons why a lot of crabs are collected. First, most Grapsidae are distributed in intertidal zones along tropical and subtropical coasts. Shenzhen is a subtropical coast city, so that Grapsidae can easily live in Shenzhen Bay. Second, sexually mature Grapsidae need to migrate to brackish or shallow waters near river mouths for reproduction. Dasha river dam is a part of Shenzhen Bay and the intertidal zone is a good place for crab’s reproduction. Environment was perfectly suitable for Grapsidae.

The first organism had been identified is *Neritina violacea*. It distributes in soft mud, rubble mound and separation dike [4]. It mostly lives in east coast of China. The second organism had been identified *Metopograpsus quadridentatus*. This crab is living in seawater and it often find in rock crevices or under rocks at low tide lines [5]. The last species had been identified is Nereididae. It originally distributed on both sides of the North Pacific [6]. Nereididae is usually finding in intertidal zone. It can also find on the rocky shore, crevices of the rocks, and the seaweed clusters.

The disadvantage of this experiment is that the rate of success is relatively low. If we didn’t collect a lot of samples, PCR identification will not provide us an effective result. Also, during sampling, those officers on the beach didn’t let us go into the mud area. Therefore, some of the organism

Table 1. A diagram of organism had been collected.

sample ID	Species	COI Species
SB-1	Sea Snail	<i>Neritina violacea</i>
SB-2	Sea Snail	
SB-3	Sea Snail	
SB-4	Crab	
SB-5	Sea Snail	
SB-6	Crab	
SB-7	Flat Worm	
SB-8	Flat Worm	
SB-9	Shrimp	
SB-10	Mudskipper	
SB-11	Crab	
SB-12	Gammarid	<i>Clithon sowerbianum*</i>
SB-13	Gammarid	
SB-14	Gammarid	
SB-15	Crab	
SB-16	Crab	
SB-17	Crab	<i>Metopograpsus quadridentatu</i>
SB-18	Crab	<i>Hyalidae*</i>
SB-19	Crab	
SB-20	Polychaete	
SB-21	Flat Worm	<i>Nereididae</i>
SB-22	Crab	
SB-23	Crab	
SB-24	Crab	
SB-25	Sea Snail	
SB-26	Mudskipper	
SB-27	Gammarid	
SB-BAR	Barnacle	

*Refers to potentially misidentify species.

had been observed that couldn't be sampled. For instance, there were many mudskippers on the mudflat and mudflat were forbidden for going. If those mudskippers were collected, the mudskippers may also be the dominate species in this area.

Shenzhen Bay's biodiversity is not great due to the reclamation. Only the organisms who were scavengers can be the dominate species. Then, the types of marine organisms living in Shenzhen Bay was very monotonous. Fortunately, the reclamation was already stopped. Shenzhen government was trying to recover the environment of Shenzhen Bay. Our study suggested that reclamation will cause large damage to marine ecological environment. More work should be done in order to protect Shenzhen Bay.

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